

DURABILITY

EFFECT OF COLD CLIMATE FACTORS ON STRENGTH AND
DURABILITY OF STRUCTURAL FIBERGLASS COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

A short information on the basic factors of cold climate is given. A methodical approach for studying and predicting the service lifetime of fibrous polymeric composites during ageing in free state (storage) and under static loading has been proposed. The approach is based on analysing both climate and composite from phenomenological and physical standpoint. For treatment of ageing in unloaded state from the phenomenological standpoint it is suggested to approximate the experimental data by the function taking into account the damage accumulation and after-curing of the polymeric matrix. The interrelation allowing one to consider additionally the effect of outside temperature is presented. The capabilities of the structural approach in studying weather resistance of one type of composites differing by the reinforcement pattern are shown. In treatment of climate from the physical standpoint the effect of cyclic freezing of absorbed water on fiberglass plastics is shown. In analyzing the ageing of fiberglass plastics under the conditions of static loading the attention has been focussed on short durability of the composite which is formally in discordance with high magnitudes of "residual" strength. A model based on the concepts of damageability, "pseudo-damageability" and critical damageability has been proposed for description of the experimental data.

INTRODUCTION

The development of reliable methods of quantitative evalua-

tion of the service life of structures made of fibrous polymeric composites with allowance for the effect of climatic factors is one of the main problems in the design of various-profile structures, especially those manufactured for the Far North regions[1].

The most typical region with cold climate is Yakutia; the basic weather data in the Yakutian ASSR over a period of 80 years are summarized in Table 1 [2].

TABLE 1
Basic weather data in Yakutia

Zone	Weather station	T e m p e r a t u r e , °C					
		Annual average	Absolute min	Absolute max	Annual drop	Annual precipitation mm	Solar radiation gJ/m ²
North	Tixi	-13.4	-54	33	87	250	3.06
Central	Yakutsk	-10.3	-64	38	102	175	3.71
Central	Oimyakon	-16.6	-71	33	104	250	3.24
South	Aldan	-6.2	-61	35	96	550	-

Aside from the tabulated data (high annual temperature drop, low precipitation, a fairly high solar radiation level) strong daily temperature fluctuations (up to 40°C) and a good many cases when temperature exceeds 0°C are characteristic of the Yakutian ASSR.

The present contribution deals with an approach to studying the service life of fibrous polymeric composites (FPC) and their structures under severe weather conditions and presents some experimental data for structural fiberglass plastics. The experimental and theoretical studies can be represented in the following general scheme (Fig. 1).

The most usual environmental effects are treated: ageing in unloaded state (storage) and under static loading. The characteristics determining the service life of fibrous polymeric composites are: "residual" strength upon ageing in unloaded state and "residual" strength and durability upon ageing under loading.

AGEING IN UNLOADED STATE (STORAGE)

Each of the constituents of combination "climate+composite" can be evaluated both from the phenomenological and physical (structural) standpoint.

As regards climate the phenomenological approach is reduced to a theoretical analysis based on the results of full-scale tests. If we apply the phenomenological approach to a composite, it is possible to formulate a semi-empirical prob-

Figure 1. General outline of the method of studying the service life of fibrous polymeric composites in cold climate conditions.

lem of describing the experimental data with subsequent extrapolation in time.

The experiments carried out in Yakutsk [1, 3, 4] have yielded a rather variegated resistance for various types of fibrous polymeric composites to longterm effect of cold climate factors.

It follows from the results tabulated in Table 2 [4] that for fiberglass plastics upon exposure in unheated warehouse during the first year a more pronounced deterioration of the mechanical properties is observed than by exposing in outdoor testing ground.

TABLE 2

Relative elastic and strength characteristics of wound fiberglass/polyester plastic* after outdoor storage in the cold climate conditions

Specimen types	Testing techniques	Climatic factors	Strength		Modulus of elasticity	
			0.5y.	1y.	0.5y.	1y.
Segments	Bending (failure due to tangential compressive stresses)	Storehouse	0.96	0.84	0.99	0.92
		Outdoor testing ground	0.95	0.93	0.99	0.98
Strips	Bending (failure due to axial tensile stresses)	Storehouse	0.96	0.91	0.90	0.80
		Outdoor testing ground	1.08	0.95	0.97	0.83
Segments	Interlaminar shear	Storehouse	0.93	0.86	0.99	0.99
		Outdoor testing ground	0.96	0.95	0.97	0.93

*The structure of a composite: circumferential winding + random reinforcement of chopped fiberglass.

Since the level of atmospheric precipitation is low, the difference in ageing in the storehouse and outdoors is practically ascribed to a comparatively high level of solar radiation which leads to fairly prolonged heating to the specimens right up to temperature of +60°C. The heating of fiberglass plastic intensifies the after-curing process of a polymeric matrix and this is naturally the cause of improvement of the mechanical properties of the composite.

In such a way, the process of after-curing of the polymeric matrix, characteristic for regions of moderate [5] and warm [6,7] climate, should be taken into account in interpretation of the results obtained by exposing fibrous polymeric composites outdoors in cold climate.

Therefore, an adequate phenomenological ageing model should involve (apart from the function of damage accumulation) also the function characterizing the attenuating process of after-curing of the matrix [8,9]. Taking this specific feature into account allows one to describe satisfactorily a fairly complex character of changes in the strength properties of fibrous polymeric composites in the first stage of exposure.

Besides the ageing effects, the service life of composite structures depends naturally on outside temperature. This problem can be reduced to consideration of the function:

$$R = F(T^{\circ}, t) \quad (1)$$

where R is the strength of a composite; T° is the outside temperature; t is the time of exposure.

Testing of fiberglass plastics has shown that the relationship (1) can approximately be expressed in the form:

$$R = R_0(T^{\circ}) - \Psi(t) \quad (2)$$

where $R_0(T^{\circ})$ is the strength of fiberglass plastic in the initial state; $\Psi(t)$ is the ageing function.

In such a way, the problem of necessity to test the exposed specimens within the range of $-60^{\circ}\text{C} \div +60^{\circ}\text{C}$ is not essential for the mentioned composites, since the test results obtained at $+20^{\circ}\text{C}$ are sufficiently informative.

Treatment of climate from the phenomenological, but composite from "structural" standpoint is reasonable in the following circumstances. In practice, it is infrequently necessary to evaluate atmospheric resistance for a definite class of laminated composites differing only by the reinforcement scheme.

In accordance with the theory of laminated media, the deformation and strength properties of fibrous polymeric composites are determined by the elastic and strength characteristics of the basic unidirectional lamina, while in accordance with micromechanics of composites - by the volume fraction and parameters of constituents and the interface. It should be expected that the extent of climate effect on various basic characteristics might be different; moreover, environmental effects on several characteristics can be inessential.

The finding of the optimal model for the given combination "type of climate - type of composite" with the help of a computer is principally not difficult, although certainly the problem of correct selection of independent experiments for obtaining the initial information still remains. Some possibilities of the given approach are shown in [9,10].

As to climate the physical approach is characterised by study of the effect of individual climatic factors or their combination on materials. As to composites, it is reasonable to restrict oneself to the assumption that the accumulating of damage in fibrous polymeric composites is practically due to

the effect of only two factors:

- 1) temperature fluctuations (thermo-elastic fatigue);
- 2) moisture, including cyclic changes in phase state.

The following fundamental results have been obtained (part of the experimental data is tabulated in Table 3 [II] in studying of composites from the phenomenological standpoint:

- 1) the various types of fibrous polymeric composites have sharply varying moisture resistance to temperature fluctuations;
- 2) for fibrous polymeric composites with low moisture resistance, the reduction in strength is manifested already during the first one or two freezing cycles.

TABLE 3

Relative strength of fibrous polymeric composites* in bending after thermal cycling in dry and wet state within the temperature range $+20^{\circ}\text{C} \dots -60^{\circ}\text{C}$

Testing techniques	Materials		
	A	B	C
2 x thermal cycle	1.02	0.96	-
2 x (thermal cycle + H ₂ O)	0.89	0.94	1.16

- *
 A - an oriented fiberglass/phenol plastic
 B - a randomly reinforced fiberglass/phenol plastic
 C - a randomly reinforced fiberglass/polyamide plastic

The data of strength reduction show a good correlation with the essential rise in moisture absorption. The measurement of this characteristic can be used as a proximate method for qualitative evaluation of probable atmospheric resistance of fibrous polymeric composites in the conditions of cold climate [12]. The treatment of climate from the physical standpoint will be useful for developing of the most efficient techniques of accelerated environmental tests on a qualitative level.

The problem of treatment both climate and composite from the physical standpoint is beyond the scope of this contribution. It is no doubt that such investigations will be useful and necessary, however, their results might have been used not for prediction of the reserve of reliability of various types of fibrous polymeric composites, but for development of new composites with elevated resistance to the effect of cold climate factors.

AGEING UNDER STATIC LOADING

Obviously, so far we are to restrict ourselves to treatment of this sufficiently complicated problem both pertaining to climate and composite from the phenomenological standpoint. The problem on the whole can be characterized as follows. Ac-

tive exposure to environmental conditions leads to appearance of the characteristic "knee" on "stress vs time" curve (Fig. 2) and, consequently, to essential decrease in service life of the structure [13, 14]. Before discussing the possibilities of quantitative description of the curves of Fig. 2, it is useful to pay attention to the following facts. In Table 4, the data of residual strength of segments cut from rings and loaded in bending in Yakutsk's conditions [4] are presented.

TABLE 4

Relative strength of fiberglass/polyester wound plastic aged under bending in cold climate conditions

Types of environmental effects	Relative applied load	Time of exposure	
		0.5 y.	1 y.
Room	0	-	-
	0.15	0.99	0.82
	0.3	0.93	0.81
Storehouse	0	0.96	0.84
	0.15	0.93	0.80
	0.3	Failure	Failure
Outdoor testing range	0	0.95	0.93
	0.15	0.88	0.70
	0.3	Failure	Failure

It is seen from the table that at the level of stresses equal to 30% of the ultimate stress in the initial state, the failure of rings exposed to storehouse and outdoor testing ground conditions is registered. On the other hand, it is notable that the residual strength of unfailed rings is fairly high. (Analogous results have been obtained in works [15,16]). In such a way, a characteristic feature of fibrous polymeric composites is the high values of "residual" strength in pre-critical stage of the structure. Of course, the given facts must caution against unjustifiably "optimistic" forecasts about durability based merely on high values of "residual" strength.

The given experimental results can be interpreted in terms of the following qualitative model (Fig. 3). In the process of "initial" quasi-static loading the reversible "pseudo-damageability" develops in the composite, which is "summed up" with damageability developing nonlinearly in time. The ultimate state of the structure is determined by the critical damageability which depends on outside temperature (ξ_{crit}^0 is the critical damageability at room temperature).

The dependency of the critical damageability on temperature can qualitatively be shown by using the experimental results of Table 5 [4].

Figure 2. Diagrams of durability. — in absence of environmental effects; - - - weak environmental effect; - · - · under severe environmental effect

Figure 3. A qualitative model for description of "residual" strength (a) and durability (b) of fiberglass plastics.

TABLE 5

The effect of environmental factors on durability of fiberglass/polyester rings (relative applied load - 0.3)

Nos.	1 stage exposure in water		2 stage exposure in air		Total damage	Critical damage	Experimental result*
	Temp. °C	Time mos	Temp. °C	Time hrs			
1	20	2	-60	2	average	maximum	-
2	20	2	+60	2	minimum	minimum	-
3	20	2	-60	4	average	maximum	-
4	20	2	+60	4	average	minimum	+
5	20	2	±60	2+2	average	minimum	+
6	20	6	-	-	maximum	average	+

*"- " rings did not fail; "+" rings failed.

On the basis of qualitative ideas of works [8,9], two versions of a semi-empirical quantitative model have been treated. This model is based on the hypothesis about selfsimilarity of the process of damage accumulation and a premise about the possibility of describing the mechanical and climatic effects by two scalar functions, obeying the principle of superposition.

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